

Effects of Teacher and Peer Mediated Instructional Approaches on Secondary School Students' Learning Outcome in Science Subjects

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Abstract

This study sought to ascertain the effects of teacher-mediated instructional approach, peer-mediated instructional approach and the combination of teacher and peer mediated instructional approaches on secondary school students' learning outcome in science subjects. The study is a quasi experimental design which adopted the pre-test, post-test, experimental group method. The population of the study was 30427 which comprised all the SS2 students in Owerri educational zone 1 in Imo State. The simple random and purposive sampling techniques were used to select one local government area and three secondary schools. The sample of the study was 120 students randomly assigned to groups. Two research questions and one null hypothesis guided the study. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 significant level. Data were collected using the researcher made achievement test duly validated and reliability coefficient of 0.76 ascertained using Cronbach Alpha. Mean was used to answer research questions, and Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypothesis. Results from the study showed that teacher-mediated instructional approach (TMIA) was significantly effective on secondary school students' learning outcome in science subjects. The results also indicated that peer-mediated instructional approach (PMIA) was significantly effective on secondary school students' learning outcome in science subjects. However, it was found that a combination of teacher and peer-mediated instructional approach (T/PMIA) was significantly more effective on secondary school students' learning outcome in science subjects than the single approaches. The researchers recommended among others that combined teacher/peer instructional approach which yielded a more positive result should be introduced for enhancement of learning outcomes.

Keywords: Learning outcome, Teacher Instructional approach and Peer instructional approach

Introduction

Psychological variable like academic achievement is a very important learning outcome that must be put into consideration during any teaching and learning processes. Academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university (Eccles, 2009). Hence, Okafor, Obi and Oguzie (2018) maintained that academic achievement is one of the most important and most objective criteria to evaluate the effectiveness of any teaching and learning process.

Science subjects have been identified as the major bedrock subjects for the transformation of our nation's economy and hence must be accorded adequate attention. According to Amalaha (2008), science and technical education are the factories for the production of the needed technologist, technicians and crafts men as well as skilled artisans and professionals who are required to turn the nation's economy around and usher in the desired technological advancement. The acquisition of appropriate scientific and technological skills is necessary to cope with the challenges presented by the involving needs of modern work place in our industries and the ever-growing non formal sector. Okoro (2010) stressed that providing access to appropriate learning experience designed to broaden skills and knowledge can increase productivity and scientifically improve the fortunes of the unemployed thereby reducing poverty and unemployment amongst our people.

It is against this background that science subjects have been accorded prime positions worldwide. It was as a result of the recognition given to o' level science subjects in the development of the individual and the nation that made them pre-requisite subjects for offering science oriented courses in the tertiary institutions and this calls for the need to teach them more effectively. Effective teaching of science subjects according to Achimugu (2011), not only help students to develop science process skills such as observing, classifying, predicting, measuring, recording data, hypothesizing, drawing inference, among others. It also enhances students' better understanding of concepts and principles which significantly contribute to their high achievement, it encourages students to be active in class, thereby discouraging abstraction, rote memorization and inattentiveness in class, it promotes the development of science attitudes such as objectivity, honesty, patience, open-mindedness. Achimugu (2009) and Onwuka (2011) pointed out that science teaching is supposed to be result oriented and students centered, and this can only be achieved when students are willing to learn and the teachers are favourably disposed, using appropriate instructional approaches and resources in teaching the students. They emphasized that teaching of science subjects should involve hands-on and minds-on. This implies that it should be activity or learner centered, students need to actively construct their own personal awareness and meaning. Science subjects are said to be effectively taught and learnt when the students' academic achievement and other learning outcomes are enhanced.

Science subjects in secondary schools are being taught by the teacher mediated instructional approach and experience of some science teachers who are WAEC examiners, WASSCE Result (2015-2017), knowledge from WAEC marking coordination every year, Seminars and workshop conducted by Science Teachers Association(STAN) which the researchers are

members and interaction with one another all reported poor learning outcome of students in science subjects and they pointed out that poor method of teaching, few science teachers, big volume of course content and no teaching period assigned to science practical in secondary schools contribute to these poor learning outcomes in science subject. Research works by Okoro (2010) and Onyewu (2012) on the improvement of science learning outcomes have recommended the employment of more science teachers which nobody knows when. These are supposed to reduce the number of students per teacher and to accommodate the ever rising size of students' population in secondary schools. Hence, the need for this study to investigate the effects of combining teacher and peer instructional approaches on students' learning outcomes in science subjects cannot be overemphasized.

The teacher-mediated instructional approach (TMIA) called the traditional teaching which has been defined by Joof (2001) as an age long traditional method of teaching in which knowledge of information is presented or transferred to learners by the teacher. In this method of teaching according to Dutta, Singh and Saxena in Dupaul (2008), the teacher dominates the authoritarian teaching – learning process and talks as an autocrat and as repository of knowledge to passive listening students. The teacher's unaided voice may not be effective in communicating to the students and the students are not given the opportunity to exhibit the science skills that are meant for science subjects which have been identified as central to teaching and learning them. These problems reduce the quality of teaching and learning science subjects and thereby result in poor learning outcomes (Achimugu, 2009).

Diana (2000) in her study titled 'students as teachers' suggested a revolutionary learning approach which is known as peer-mediated instructional approach (PMIA) as ideal for teaching science subjects. Peer-mediated instructional approach is defined as an approach in which one child instructs another (Damon & Phelp, 2011). Studies by Ukwuoma (2009) and Diana (2000) find peer teaching to be very effective in instructing both large and small classes. In large classes, it is said to reduce the distance between teachers and students and it is suggested as a noise reduction strategy and very good for teaching science subjects.

In peer teaching, the peer teacher is not very far removed from the tutee in authority or knowledge, nor has the peer teacher any special claims to peer teaching offers moral education as the tutors through the exercise of responsibility have the opportunity to learn and care for others. They also develop a sense of personal worth, growth and responsibility. Riessman (1993) in Ukwuoma (2009) observed that peer teaching provides flexibility of education at reasonable cost especially when mixed ability groups require more individual attention and consequently more work hours or man power. This can be provided by peer teachers at no extra cost. The class teacher can be relieved from routine tasks to attend to specialist educational activities or other important issues. Peer teaching has however, been highly criticized by some experts (Ukwuoma, 2009). These scholars argued that in peer teaching, both tutors and tutees are students and most times in the same class, the peer teachers who are non experts in the subjects or topics they teach may not be adequately prepared to manage the social and emotional demands of the tutees. Ukwuoma also alleged that the teachers' role and authority in the class may be threatened by the peer mediated learning. Again, according to critics of peer-mediated instruction, the approach to

teaching does not succeed among senior learners because of the indispensable roles to be carried out by trained teachers. For these reasons, this study combined the two instructional approaches as one instructional approach to see its effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of teacher-mediated instructional approach, peer-mediated instructional approach and a combination of teacher/peer-mediated instructional approach on secondary school students' learning outcomes in science subjects. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain:

1. The effects of teacher-mediated instructional approach, peer-mediated instructional approach and teacher with peer mediated instructional approaches on students' learning outcomes in Chemistry.
2. The comparative effects of teacher-mediated instructional approach, peer-mediated instructional approach and teacher with peer mediated instructional approach on students' learning outcome in science subject (Chemistry test) after the treatment.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What difference exists in the pre-test and post-test mean of subjects taught with TMIA, PMIA and T/PMIA at post-test?
2. What differences exist in mean of students' achievement in science subject (Chemistry) test after the treatment – TMIA, PMIA and T/ PMIA?

Hypothesis

This following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean of students' learning outcome in science subject (chemistry) test after the treatments of teacher/peer mediated approach, teacher-mediated approach and peer-mediated approach.

Method

The design of this study is quasi-experimental which adopted the pre-test/post test experimental method. The study involved three experimental groups. Experimental group 1 received the peer-mediated instruction (T1) as treatment, experimental group 2 received the teacher-mediated instruction (T2) as treatment and experimental group 3 received the combined teacher / peer mediated instruction (T3) as treatment. This study was carried out in Imo State of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 30427 students. These were distributed among 272 senior secondary schools in the state. The information was collected from records available at the Research and Statistics Department of Secondary Education Management Board Owerri, Imo State. SS2 class satisfied the requirement for the study and was also available for the study. Chemistry, one of the science subjects was used since all the science subjects cannot be used for the study. The sample for this study consisted of 120 chemistry students from three selected secondary schools in educational zone 1 of Imo State. The simple random and purposive sampling techniques were used for the sampling. Intact groups of all the SS2 chemistry students

in each of the schools were used. The instrument used for data collection was a self-made questionnaire titled “Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT)” which consisted of 50 multiple choice items. Experts validated the instrument and the reliability coefficients of 0.76 was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha. The schools for the study were assigned to experimental groups 1, 2 and 3. The SS2 chemistry students which formed intact groups in the laboratories were used for the study. To get the baseline data for the study, the three groups were pre-tested. After which, the instructional approaches commenced. At the end of the instruction, another test (post-test) was given to the three groups. The teaching experiments lasted for 6 weeks. The researchers wrote all the lesson notes and produced enough copies for all the participating peer teachers. The mean was used to answer each research questions while Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and F-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research question one: What difference exists in the pre-test and post-test mean of subject taught with TMIA, and T/PMIA at post-test?

Table 1: Mean scores of students in chemistry pretest scores and their scores at posttest when taught through TMIA, PMIA and T/PMIA.

Group	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
TMIA Group			
Pretest	15.98	3.33	42.66
Posttest	58.64	7.80	
PMIA Group			
Pretest	16.63	4.38	51.43
Posttest	54.33	11.86	
T/PMIA Group			
Pretest	16.63	4.38	51.43
Posttest	68.06	10.70	

Table 1 shows that the mean scores of the pretest and posttest when used TMIA are 15.98 and 58.64 respectively, and that the difference in the means is 42.66. It can be therefore inferred that there is a difference in mean scores of the pretest and posttest when used TMIA and posttest group achieved higher than the pretest group meaning that using TMIA there was effective learning outcome by gaining a mean of 42.66

Similarly, Table 1 shows that the mean scores of the pretest and posttest when used PMIA are 16.63 and 54.33 respectively and that the difference in the means is 51.43. It can be therefore inferred that there is a difference in mean scores of the pretest and posttest when used PMIA and posttest group achieved higher than the pretest group meaning that using PMIA. Thus, there was effective learning outcome by gaining a mean of 51.43. The results above equally show that the mean-gain of the methods PMIA and TMIA are 51.43 and 42.66 respectively. Meaning that while TMIA is effective, T/PMIA is more effective in this experiment.

Research Question Two: What differences exist in mean of students’ achievement in Chemistry test after the treatments – TMIA, PMIA and T/PMIA?

Table 2: Mean of students' achievement in chemistry after the treatment PMIA, TMIA and T/PMIA

Groups	Posttest Mean	SD	Mean Difference
TMIA	59.0	7.33	11.8
PMIA	54.09	7.33	8.88
TMIA	59.9		
T/PMIA	67.97	13.58	11.86
PMIA	54.09		
TMIA	59.9	8.97	
T/PMIA	67.97		

Table 2 shows that the mean score of the TMIA group at posttest is 59.07 and the mean score of Teacher/Peer mediated instructional approach T/PMIA is 67.97. The mean scores of the TMIA and T/PMIA groups at posttest are 59.00 and 67.97 respectively. The difference in the means is 8.97. It can therefore be inferred that there is a difference in the mean scores of the TMIA and T/PMIA at posttest and T/PMIA group achieved higher than the TMIA group at posttest.

Hypothesis: Ho: There is no significant difference in the mean of student's achievement in chemistry test after the treatments TMIA, PMIA and T/PMIA.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) F-test on the mean scores of the three treated groups in researcher made posttest.

Source	SS	Df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P≥0.05
Corrected						
Model	3635.25	3	12111.75			
Intercept	22721.92	1	22721.92			
Pretest	84.33	2	1727.99	16.84	3.80	0.05 .000
Error	11906.34	116	102.64			
Total	443113.00	120				
Corrected						
Total	15541.59	119				

Table 3 shows that the F-computed (16.84) is greater than F-critical (3.80) and the level of significance (0.05) is greater than the probability (0.00). This result rejects the null hypothesis that there are no significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in the mean scores of the three treated groups in researcher made posttest and accepts the alternate hypothesis that there are significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the mean scores of the three treated groups in researcher made post test. A pair-wise Comparison test was ran on the mean scores to find out which of the groups significantly achieved higher.

Table 4: Pair-wise Comparison of the achievement of the three treated groups.

Groups	Posttest Mean	Mean Difference	Probability	Significant (P<0.05)
Teacher-mediated Instrumental Approach	59.00	8.88	0.001	Yes
Combined Teacher & Peer Mediated Approach	67.97			
Peer-mediated Instrumental Approach	54.34			
Combined Teacher and Peer mediated Approach	67.97	13.63	0.000	Yes

Table 4 shows that for TMIA and T/PMIA groups, probability (0.001) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This implies that there is significance in the mean scores of the two treated groups at posttest and T/PMIA group significantly achieved higher than the TMIA group.

For PMIA and T/PMIA groups, probability (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This implies that there is significant difference in the mean scores of the two treated groups at posttest and T/PMIA group significantly achieved higher than the PMIA group.

Discussion

The findings have been made on the effects of teacher mediated, the peer mediated and the combined teacher and peer-mediated instructional approaches on students learning outcomes (academic achievement) in science subject using chemistry” Resui’s of the analysis showed that there is difference in mean scores of the pretest and posttest of students when taught with TMIA, PMIA and combined T/PMIA and posttest groups achieved higher than the pretest groups meaning that using TMIA, PMIA and combined T/PMIA there were effective in achieving learning outcome. The findings of this study showed that though the three approaches were effective, the combined teacher and peer instructional approach proved to be more effective than the other two in achieving and enhancing learning outcomes. The reason for the difference may be due to the mode of implementation of the approaches and its effectiveness may be attributed to the steps involved in the peer instructional approach and the facilitating activities of the teacher in the classroom. Students who were taught by the combined teacher and peer-mediated instructional approach were more active in class than those who studied under the teacher or peer mediated approaches. This finding is in agreement with the views of Gartner and Riesman, 1993 in Ukwuoma (2009) asserted that peers with teachers by their side communicate to their peers better than the teachers because they are cognitively closer to the students than the teachers and this enhances students’ achievement. Cazden (2006) seem to agree with the above finding by stating that peers with teachers by their side were more accurate in determining from non-verbal behaviours whether classmates understood lesson. With reference to data analyzed in the study,

the students' performance is attributed to the various features of combined Teacher and peer-mediated instructional approach. These features include increase in students class participation, peer-teachers' language, learning in small groups, students playing the teachers' role in teaching and evaluation, teachers' supportive role rather than dominating role, and friendly relationship among students.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the academic achievement of the students who were taught using the combined teacher and peer mediated instructional approaches was higher than that of the students who were taught with the teacher or peer mediated instructional approaches and that combined teacher and peer mediated instructional approach can be effectively used to improve students' learning outcome in science subjects. This implies that teachers could raise the learning outcomes of students in chemistry and other science subjects by adjusting their methods of instructing science subjects without necessarily increasing cost in finance and time.

The finding also indicates that students prefer teachers playing supportive roles instead of authoritarian role in the class. It also implies that combined Teacher and Peer-mediated instructional approach could be used to create a cordial students-teacher relationship. The study finds that the combined Teacher and peer mediated instructional approach encourages friendly and cordial relationship among students. Finally, this approach to instruction could be applied to build up team spirit and group life among students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it has been recommended that:

- (a) A system of combined teacher and peer mediated instructional approach should be introduced in Secondary Schools. This should involve teachers preparing the lesson plans/notes while students deliver the lessons to their classmates. The mode of instruction may specially comprise the following features: splitting the class into small learning groups: peer teaching of the model of peer reciprocal teaching, peer grading, adequate use of instructional materials and teachers supportive role.
- (b) If as a result of the circumstances of a school or a teacher, it is not possible to fully carry out the combined Teacher and peer mediated instructional approach, some of its strategies such as peer grading and small group-study sessions may be used by teachers. A teacher could encourage students to constitute small study groups which may meet from time to time to discuss the materials that have been or will be presented to them. Many students find such small study group session very useful in clarifying difficult aspect of any learning task.

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